

ISic2747

I.Sicily inscription 2747

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Euryelos, found during work to clear and clarify the dipylon in the fortifications

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 24432

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. βα[σιλ]ε[ὺς --- β]ασιλ[έως --- τὰς] κρη[πίδας --- ἐτέλεσεν]

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1994

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645150

PHI 332962

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